

Notice:

1. Pulse Rate
2. Pulse Regularity
3. Pulse Volume

Introduction to Pulse

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Clinical Pulse Examination

- Pulse examination is one of the oldest diagnostic tools.
- In Ayurveda → known as Nadi Pariksha, an important aspect of Ashtavidha Pariksha.
- Modern Medicine also adopt the Nadi Pariksha as arterial pulse examination as a clinical sign to assess cardiovascular status.
- Non-invasive, quick, inexpensive, and provides valuable information.

Definition

- Modern: Pulse is the tactile arterial palpation of the heartbeat, transmitted through arterial walls due to left ventricular contraction.
- Ayurveda: Nadi (pulse) is the manifestation of Vata, Pitta, Kapha dosha movements, felt at the radial artery.

Sites of Pulse Examination

Temporal

Carotid

Axillary

Brachial

Radial

Femoral

popliteal

posterior tibial

dorsalis pedis

Sites of Pulse Examination

- Radial artery (most common)
- Carotid artery
- Brachial artery
- Femoral artery
- Dorsalis Pedis
- Posterior Tibial

**Location of
the Radial Artery**

Forceps
Grasping
Radial
Artery

Technique

- Patient relaxed, arm supported, palm upwards.
- * Examiner uses three fingers (index, middle, ring) on radial artery.
- Note:
 - Rate
 - Rhythm
 - Volume
 - Vessel wall condition
 - Character

Rate

- Normal: 60–100/min (adults).
- Tachycardia: >100 /min
- Bradycardia: <60 /min

Rhythm

- Regular
- Irregular (regularly irregular vs irregularly irregular, e.g., Atrial fibrillation)

Volume

- Indicates stroke volume.
- Low volume: shock, heart failure
- High volume: fever, thyrotoxicosis

Condition of Vessel Wall

- Atherosclerosis –
thick, hard vessel.

Equality

- Compare both sides:
absence/asymmetry → arterial obstruction,
coarctation of aorta.

Character of pulse

- Character means the shape and feel of the pulse wave during palpation. It reflects stroke volume, arterial compliance, and vascular resistance.

1. Normal Pulse

- Smooth upstroke, gentle downstroke.
- Not too strong or weak.

2. Abnormal Pulse Characters

- Anacrotic pulse – AS (aortic stenosis)
- Collapsing (water hammer) – Aortic regurgitation (AR)
- Bisferiens – HOCM, AR + AS
- Pulsus paradoxus – cardiac tamponade
- Pulsus alternans – LV failure

Anacrotic Pulse

- Feature: Slow rising, low amplitude, with a notch on the upstroke.
- Cause: Severe aortic stenosis (AS).
- Clinical feel: “Heaving but delayed.”

Collapsing Pulse (Water Hammer Pulse)

- Feature: High volume, rapid upstroke, then sudden collapse.
- Causes:
 - Aortic regurgitation (AR)
 - PDA (Patent ductus arteriosus)
 - High-output states (thyrotoxicosis, fever, anemia)
 - Clinical feel: If you elevate patient's arm, pulse collapses rapidly.

Bisferiens Pulse

- Feature: Double peak in systole.
- Causes:
 - AR with AS
 - Hypertrophic obstructive cardiomyopathy (HOCM)
- Mnemonic: “Two beats in one.”

Pulsus Alternans

- Feature: Alternating strong and weak beats, despite regular rhythm.
- Cause: Severe left ventricular failure.
- Clinical clue: Best felt at radial artery with light pressure.

Pulsus Paradoxus

- Feature: Exaggerated fall (>10 mmHg) in systolic BP during inspiration \rightarrow weak/absent pulse in inspiration.
- Causes:
 - Cardiac tamponade
 - Severe asthma, COPD
 - Constrictive pericarditis
- Tip: "Pulse disappears in inspiration"

Dicrotic Pulse

- Feature: Double pulse, one in systole and another in diastole (dicrotic notch palpable).
- Causes:
 - Low cardiac output states (typhoid fever, septicemia).

Thready Pulse

- Feature: Very weak, rapid, difficult to palpate.
- Cause:
Shock, severe hypovolemia

Bounding Pulse

- Feature: Strong, forceful pulse, difficult to obliterate.
- Causes:
 - Fever
 - Anemia
 - Pregnancy
 - Aortic regurgitation

Clinical Importance

- Quick cardiovascular assessment.
- Helps in diagnosing heart diseases, arrhythmias, shock, dehydration, thyroid disorders, etc.

Thanks

- www.drpankajjain.com